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giazoidze@yahoo.com***Abstract**

In the conditions of modern globalization, education creates the strongest foundations for individual and national economic security, which becomes an important stable and sustainable political, economic, social and environment precondition. A market economy functions better if there is universal competition. In addition, attention should be paid to economic threats related to other security sectors. It is important that the education system sets out a strategy to prepare the generations with the knowledge and skills necessary for the effective realization of a country's competitive advantage in order to grow the national economy.

On the one hand, a strong sense of personal security lays the foundation for the proper functioning of political and socio-economic institutions and thus promotes sustainable economic development and national security; In turn, a high level of national security guarantees sustainable personal security. States and education agencies should have clear measurements of the plans and processes that ensure the successful implementation of relevant projects.

Economic security can be considered as a key indicator for the general security of the state. Achieving economic security also makes other levels of security easier to achieve. Environmental security in the country largely depends on economic and political security. Security analysis in all sectors separately and their importance for the overall security of the country is crucial for regional and international security.

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JEL Classification: *A20, F52, F52*

I. INTRODUCTION

An important component of security, such as the economy, has not received adequate attention for a long time. At the present stage, economic security is given priority in strengthening the country's defense capabilities and physical security. The interrelationships between individual components of general security definitely need further research and study.

Education plans, ways of implementation and results, in turn, are an important determinant of economic security. If the education system has a proper political mandate, if it has internal resources and external support for education reform, then the relevant priorities of the mandate will be properly identified, a plan will be drawn, existing resources will be properly mobilized and managed to deliver quality education.

Quality education lays the strongest foundations for individual (micro-level) and national (macro-level) economic security, making it an indisputable precondition for a stable and sustainable political, economic and social environment.

II. INCREASED IMPORTANCE OF ECONOMIC SECURITY

We will say nothing new if we note that sustainable peace and sustainable development are not only determined by the strength of the developed defense.

Military security is the longest approach to the study of general security, while economic security is a relatively new, albeit widely accepted approach. The oil-related shocks of the 1970s prompted security experts to acknowledge the importance of economics for the well-being of nation states and their citizens. The collapse of Soviet-style communism and the spread of the economic system based on a market economy made visible the need to pay attention to this area of public life.

In the 1991 work "People, States and Fear" by Tony Buzan (English writer and education consultant) changed the direction of understanding security levels and sectors. He outlined individuals, states, and international systems at three levels. Another work, "New Models of Global Security in the Twenty-First Century," addressed the political, military, economic, social, and environmental areas of security.

Buzan noted in 1991 that it is quite difficult to define economic security, as the main feature of the market economic system is the so-called "Perpetual threat" competitive and unpredictable system. i.e. a market economy functions better if there is universal competition and a constant threat of failure. Consequently, economic security seems at first glance incompatible with global market mechanisms such as growing free trade and increasing competition. In addition, attention should be paid to economic threats related to other security sectors. The areas of security are interdependent and mutually conditioned. For example, economic threat may also affect the internal political stability of a state. It is clear that military security depends on economic security in terms of budget constraints.

The study of economic security should be based on how the state uses economic mechanisms to maintain its territorial integrity, the degree to which it meets the needs of its citizens, how it maintains political and cultural independence, and how it manages to avoid foreign military aggression (B. Horgan, et al., 2008).).

There are assumptions that economic and financial security should be considered and analyzed in one space. For example, it is clarified that economic and financial security is the continuity of the existence of a stable income or other resources to ensure living standards now and in the foreseeable future, which includes probable continuing solvency; Forecasting the future income of an individual or other economic entity (e.g., the country as a whole); Employment or job security. Financial security means managing the money and savings of an individual or family. Economic security also combines the productivity levels of society, the monetary allowance of unemployed citizens, and the consequences of all this.

III. THE IMPACT OF EDUCATION ON THE LEVEL OF ECONOMIC SECURITY

As early as 1935, after the Great Depression, Lucien B. Keane tried to link the shortcomings of the education sector to economic unreliability and insecurity. This was one of the first attempts. Creating a sustainable future is based on a peaceful society. Education becomes the main driving force for achieving interdependent goals.

Improving education for peace and sustainable development will have a long-term impact not only on teaching outcomes and the quality of education, but also on accelerating the development of a more inclusive, equitable and fair society. This will encourage a positive school culture and increased student engagement; the introduction of practices that are consistent with the values of equality and mutual respect; Develop skills and attitudes that will enable citizens to create healthy and fulfilling living conditions. This includes the desire to collaborate and achieve goals together, problem-solving skills, education in information and communication technologies, and social and cultural competencies (UNESCO, 2019).

It should be noted that education does not involve the interpretation of facts. It is much more than just remembering facts and a simple understanding of terms and concepts. A good education should enable the learner and then the student to transform memorized and understood knowledge, apply it and reflect on it to deal with real-life challenges in order to achieve the basic goals of economic security at the personal and national levels. These two levels lead to mutual benefits. On the one hand, a strong sense of personal security lays the foundation for the proper functioning of political and socio-economic institutions and thus promotes sustainable economic development and national security; In turn, a high level of national security guarantees sustainable personal security. Here we will specify the Anglo-Saxon and Asian approaches. According to the Anglo-Saxon approach, education is considered at the individual level and is a determinant of the economic security of each of us. The Asian approach treats education at the national level and trains a workforce with quality skills.

Economic security itself is considered on two levels. One is the individual level, which refers to education as a determinant of an individual's economic security, while education at the national level must ensure the training of a quality and competitive workforce. The education system must devise a strategy to prepare the generations with the knowledge and skills necessary for the effective realization of a country's competitive advantage. Clearly, the goal is to grow the national economy.

Unstable governments, inequality, and a lack of skilled labor increase economic threats. If the education sector fails to meet these challenges, national security will not be protected either. Education is a key component of a strong economy (Brown, 2010).

The effectiveness of education is a powerful tool for economic development and social transformation and brings independence and self-confidence at both the individual and country level.

In 2010, Arne Duncan, the US Secretary of Education, addressed the Council of Foreign Affairs on the issue of educated citizens: "America's success depends on the success of individual citizens simply because the progress of humanity depends directly on the progress of the nation. I believe that education has immeasurable potential for growth and progress in the 21st century." (Shiplett et al. 2011: 83).

IV. EDUCATION AS A PUBLIC PRODUCT

Ideally, education strategy and principles should be derived from politics, but education needs to always be above politics. Is that really happening?

Public education organizations are always dependent on government funding. That is why they are often limited by political views and even directly influenced. One of the differences between public and private sector organizations is that they are accountable to the public at different levels. The education sector is uniquely responsible to the outside world and the public. Public sector organizations are governed by political and regulatory requirements. If political decisions about reforms are slowed down and delayed, then innovative and talented ideas of teaching also recede. In other cases, schools and universities are inflexible and inadequately slow to respond appropriately to planned policy changes, as most teachers have an overwhelmingly conservative approach to their duties.

Schools and universities often have difficulties in adapting to the environment as well. The Ministry of Education is an example of a mixed system of government. Proper response of the internal environment to public expectations, reflection on national policy development goals and compliance with development paths is a difficult task. Education is a cumbersome system, somewhat inflexible, and therefore it is difficult to reach consensus on development directions. This is largely due to the rapidly changing political, economic and financial environment, and in part to the insufficient number of teachers with the necessary skills.

Strategy and its directions are seldom defined consistently and do not reflect the pre-defined and agreed goals and objectives of quality education. Therefore, it is almost impossible or very insignificant to see the difference between 0.5% and 5% of GDP spent on education. Challenges in education alone cannot be overcome with large funding; especially if it is impossible to compare the qualitative results obtained with these costs. The result is that in most cases graduates of different levels of educational institutions and the results of standardized tests are often insufficient to assess strategic progress and plan for future reforms. Governments lack the experience and political will to demand reasonable reports that clearly show the links between the goals set by the system and the results achieved. Consensus needs to be reached on what direction the system should take in order to avoid stagnation in the reform process. This, in turn, will guarantee that graduates of educational institutions will use the real maximum of their capabilities to the society and contribute to sustainable economic development.

This goal can be better achieved if the government issues a clear mandate to the system. The mandate will create a solid ground for making realistic plans for the development of the system. Some examples show how governments give orders to improve economic education and at the same time give directions to the education system. For example, the mandate states: "... to renew the curriculum and assessment practices for teaching such global competencies as are necessary for the modern and future economy. These competencies are critical thinking, problem solving skills, innovation, creativity, entrepreneurship, self-organization, collaboration, communication, global citizenship and sustainability." Further schools and universities can break up this mandate into parts, formulate learning topics and directions that are relevant to each part, improve curricula and syllabi, teach teachers and instructors. Thus, an effective circle will lead the country to continuous and sustainable development.

International institutions work on the general framework of quality education. The UN sustainable development goal for education provides a key direction: "By 2030, all students need to acquire the knowledge and skills that will contribute to sustainable development. This will be possible through education in areas such as self-sustaining development and sustainable style of living, human rights, gender equality, the establishment and strengthening of a culture of peace and non-violence, world citizenship, respect for cultural diversity and the contribution of cultures to sustainable development."

States and education agencies should have clear measurements of the plans and processes that ensure the successful implementation of mandates and related projects.

V. DISADVANTAGES IN MEASURING EDUCATION OUTCOMES

Education is a difficult system to evaluate. Ideally, supportive education funding reflects the meaningful and effective links between plans and resource constraints. Resource constraints often force educational institutions to increase classes without further necessary changes.

Some authors believe that evaluation in this area is necessary in terms of budget spending efficiency: "It is clear that we should use the concept of economy in the analysis of education as a public product. It is the evaluation that should separate priorities, rational choice and allocation of available resources to achieve the goals as much as possible, i.e. "Measures that serve to maximize results should be evaluated." (Siwińska, J., 2003) Figure 1 below outlines the links between education resources and system outcomes.

There are areas of economic activity where it is almost impossible to measure the level of results or achievements on the way to the desired goals. Defense and education are similar areas in this regard. For

example, the effectiveness of defense as a public product can only be measured by the outcome of war - the armed forces either win or lose the war: ... the ultimate test of the effectiveness of the military is war, but this is, of course, an “unacceptable prospect.” (Schick, 1980). Exactly the same, the outcome of education as a second public product can be measured as the ultimate desired achievement of any country and society - the ability to survive in extremely difficult political, economic, social and environmental conditions. Quantitative indicators such as the number of school and college graduates, the number of trained and retrained teachers, or even changes in the curriculum do not fully reflect the effective use and management of budget funds for education reforms.

VI. CONCLUSION

Economic security can be considered as a key indicator for the general security of the state. Studies have shown that other levels of security can be achieved more easily by achieving economic security. Environmental security in the country largely depends on economic and political security. Security analysis in all sectors separately and their importance for the overall security of the country is crucial for regional and international security as well.

The existence of a strong link between education and economic security is no longer considered controversial. The consequences of the education system can lead to two opposite things: enhance the economic security of a country, or, conversely, make its economy easily vulnerable.

The education system should ensure the development of the system’s internal skills to keep pace with

modern rapidly changing demands. Competitiveness-oriented education is a strong driver of the country's economic growth. If governments' efforts in this direction are failed, then education management will not be able to protect itself from compromise and dysfunction.

New measures of education system outcomes need to be developed and implemented to reflect and meet the evaluation system's goal of achieving sustainable economic security and peace.

VI. REFERENCES

1. Veshapidze, S., Zubiashvili, T. (2020). About the Origins of Modern Geoeconomic Foundations of Georgia. *Ecoforum Journal* 9 (2).
2. Veshapidze, Sh., Karalashvili, Sh., (2018). Pension Reform in Georgia. *Refereed International Journal Ecoforum*. Vol. 7. №2.
3. Veshapidze, S., Darbaidze, M., Beridze, T., (2016). Euro-Atlantic values: what tie up us. *Universal*. pp. 230-235.
4. Veshapidze, S., (2020). Religion and national values in Georgia. *International Scientific Collection*, Volume 3, pp. 33-36.
5. Veshapidze, S., Mchedlishvili, Z., (2020). From Ilia Chavchavadze's Economic Views: Competition, Private Property and International Trade. *Ecoforum Journal* 9 (2).
6. Gvelesiani, R., (2019). The problem of making optimal decisions on the implementation of economic policy objectives. 2nd International Conference on Business, Management & Economics, Vienna.
7. Gvelesiani, R., (2015). The Influence of Interest Groups on Economic Policy and Its Contradictory Results. *Journal of Academy of Business and Economics*, IABE 15 (2), 35-40.
8. Gvelesiani, R., (2020). FORMATION OF THE INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEURSHIP CULTURE: CAPABILITIES AND PROBLEMS. *Ecoforum Journal* 9 (1).
9. Gvelesiani, R., (2019). The problem of compliance of the framework conditions of the policy of economic order with the basic social values. *Ivane Javakishvili Tbilisi State University Press*.
10. Gvelesiani, R., (2019). Conflict of economic interests-an identifying form of contradictory interrelation of the basic public values. *Ivane Javakishvili Tbilisi State University Press*.
11. Kharashvili, E., (2016). Small Farm Diversification Opportunities in Viticulture-Winemaking sector in Georgia. *International Journal of Social, Behavioral, Educational, Economic, Business*.
12. Kharashvili, E., Erkomaishvili, G., Chavleishvili, M. (2015). Problems faced by the agricultural sector and agribusiness development strategy in Georgia, *International Science Index 107*. *International Journal of Social, Behavioral, Educational, Economic and Management Engineering*. Volume 9, Issue 11.
13. Kharashvili, E., (2011). Problems of Competition and Competitiveness in Agro-Food Products Sector in Georgia. *Universali*, Tbilisi.
14. Kharashvili, E., (2015). Farm diversification and the corresponding policy for its implementation in Georgia, *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*. *International Journal of Social, Education, Economics and Management Engineering*. Vol., 9. Issue 5.
15. Kharashvili, E., (2018). The Impact of Preferential Agro Credit on the Development of Agribusiness in Georgia. *Ecoforum Journal* 7 (1).
16. Kharashvili, E., Gechbaia, B., Mamuladze, G., (2018). Vegetable market competitive advantages of Georgian product and competition challenges. *Innovative Marketing* 14 (3), 8-16.
17. Kharashvili, E., Chavleishvili, M., Natsvaladze, M., (2014). Trends and prospects for the development of Georgian wine market.
18. Silagadze, A., Atanelishvili T., (2011). The Potential of the Agrarian Sector of Georgia—Priorities of the Sustainable Development of Agriculture. *Tbilisi, TSU*, 418-419.
19. Silagadze, A., Zubiashvili, T., (2016). Georgia's economy against the background of the associate agreement with the European Union. *International Journal of Business and Management Studies* 5 (2), 533-540.
20. Silagadze, A., Tvalchrelidze, A., Zubiashvili, T., Atanelishvili, T., (2016). Aspects of China's economic Development. *Ecoforum* 5 (1).
21. Silagadze, A., (2014). Integration Economic Indicators of the EU and Some Issues of Development of Post-Soviet Countries—New Associate Members of the EU. *Journ. Revista Moldovenească de Drept Internațional și Relații Internaționale*. Issue 3. pp. 78-83.
22. Силагадзе, А., Атанелишвили, Т., (2010). Некоторые вопросы экономических доктрин в Грузии. *Москва, «Взфэи»*, 51с.
23. Tvalchrelidze, A., Silagadze, A., (2013). Macroeconomic model for oil-exporting countries. *Central Asia and the Caucasus* 14 (4), 118-144.
24. Zubiashvili, T., (2012). Educational and Labor Emigration of Youth from Georgia. the book: *Youth Employment: Challenges and Opportunities*. The West University of Timisoara, Romania. "Eurostampa. 317-327.
25. Zubiashvili, T., Veshapidze, S. (2019). Labour Emigration and Employment in Georgia. *Humanities and Social Sciences Review* 9 (01), 127-136.
26. Brown, S. (2010). *Education and Economic Security*, Ohio: College Presidents Conference.
27. Buzan, Barry. (1991). "New Patterns of Global Security in the Twenty-First Century." *International Affairs* (Royal Institute of International Affairs 1944-) 67.3 (1991): 431-451.
28. Buzan, Barry. (1981), *People, States and Fear: An Agenda For International Security Studies in the Post-Cold War Era*. 1st edition, 2nd Edition. Hertfordshire: Harvester Wheatsheet, 1991 and 2008 with a new preface from the author.
29. Horrihan, B., Karasik, Th., Lalgee, R. (2008), *Security Studies in Encyclopedia of Violence, Peace, & Conflict* (Second Edition), pp. 1892-1900
30. Shiplett, M.H, Russell, W., Khademian, A.M., Gant, L.P. (2011), 'A well-educated workforce: vital component of National and economic Security', in: Ronis, S.R. (ed.), *Economic Security. Neglected dimension of National Security*, Washington: National Defence University Press: 83.
31. Siwińska J., [2003], *Sektor publiczny w gospodarce*, w :Bednarski, M., Wilkin, J. (red.), *Ekonomiadlaprawnikowinietylko*, LexisNexis, Warszawa.
32. Gechbaia, B., Kharashvili, E., Mushkudiani, Z., (2019). The trends of producing agro-food products and export innovative marketing strategy in Georgia. *Economics. Ecology. Socium*. Vol., 3, Issue 3.